

ENUMERATION OF GENERALIZED HOOK PARTITIONS¹

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Abstract

We determine the generating functions of the classes of integer partitions whose Ferrers diagrams fit into a hook shape and into the intersection of two different hook shapes, respectively. Our proof is based on a purely combinatorial argument related to a special decomposition of the partitions under consideration.

1. Introduction

In the remarkable paper [2], Berele and Regev showed the relevance of the class of integer partitions whose Ferrers diagrams fit inside a hook-shape figure in the context of the representation theory of Lie superalgebras. Thus, this kind of *generalized hook partition* can be considered a combinatorial object of some importance. In their work, Berele and Regev found, among other things, interesting formulas concerning some recursions on the number of semistandard Young tableaux associated with these partitions, as well as asymptotic results on the behavior of their generating function. Much later, Orellana and Zabrocki [5] provided an expression for this generating function, but their formula is quite involved and does not have a direct combinatorial meaning.

The aim of the present paper is to give a simple closed formula for the generating function of the above mentioned class of partitions. Our proof relies on a direct combinatorial argument and is the main object of Section 2. In Section 3 we generalize our argument to the

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case of the intersection of two different hook shapes, thus obtaining the related generating function. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first enumerative result concerning this more general combinatorial situation. We remark that also this latter class of partitions has been proved useful in the representation theory of Lie superalgebras, in connection with the module decomposition of supersymmetric powers of matrices [6].

2. (h, k) -hook partitions

For any two positive integers k, h , an integer partition λ is called a (h, k) -hook partition when its Ferrers diagram fits inside a hook shape of k rows and h columns.

Figure 1: The $(2, 3)$ -hook partition $(7, 5, 3, 2, 1, 1)$.

We denote by $\mathcal{P}_{h,k}$ ($\mathcal{P}_{h,k}(n)$) the set of (h, k) -hook partitions (of n). From a combinatorial point of view, it is clear that $|\mathcal{P}_{h,k}(n)| = |\mathcal{P}_{k,h}(n)|$. In particular, $|\mathcal{P}_{k,0}(n)| = |\mathcal{P}_{0,k}(n)|$ is the cardinality of the set of partitions of n into at most k parts (or into parts less than or equal to k). Thus, if we set $p_{h,k}(n) = |\mathcal{P}_{h,k}(n)|$, we get immediately:

$$p_{k,0}(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} p_{k,0}(n)x^n = \prod_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{1-x^i}.$$

The next theorem gives a simple formula to compute the generating function $p_{h,k}(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} p_{h,k}(n)x^n$ for arbitrary $h, k \in \mathbf{N}$. This result has been first announced in [4], as an application of a general approach to integer partitions based on the ECO method. Here we propose a new proof of such a result, which is direct and independent from the ECO method. The interest of the present proof lies also in the possibility of generalizing it to the case of the intersection of two hooks.

Theorem 2.1 For any $h, k \in \mathbf{N}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_{h,k}(x) &= p_{k,0}(x) \cdot \sum_{s=0}^h x^{s(k+1)} p_{s,0}(x) \\
 &= \prod_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{1-x^i} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{x^{k+1}}{1-x} + \dots + \frac{x^{h(k+1)}}{(1-x) \dots (1-x^h)} \right). \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Any (h, k) -hook partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k, \lambda_{k+1}, \dots, \lambda_r)$ can be uniquely decomposed as follows: the subpartition $\lambda^{(1)} = (\lambda_{k+2}, \dots, \lambda_r)$ of the last $r - k - 1$ parts ($\lambda^{(1)}$ can be empty, of course); the rectangular-shaped subpartition $\lambda^{(2)} = (s^{k+1})$, where $s = \lambda_{k+1}$ (also $\lambda^{(2)}$ can be empty; this occurs, for instance, when $\lambda^{(1)}$ is empty too); and the subpartition $\lambda^{(3)} = (\lambda_1 - s, \dots, \lambda_k - s)$ (we consider only those parts $\lambda_i - s$ which are positive). This decomposition of λ is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The decomposition of λ defined in the proof of Theorem 2.1.

When s runs from 0 to h we get all the partitions of $\mathcal{P}_{h,k}$ precisely once. Therefore, passing to the generating functions, we have:

$$p_{h,k}(x) = p_{k,0}(x) \cdot \sum_{s=0}^h x^{s(k+1)} p_{s,0}(x),$$

which completes the proof. □

Example. Ordinary hook partitions correspond to $(1, 1)$ -hook partitions, hence their generating function is

$$p_{1,1}(x) = \frac{1 - x + x^2}{(1 - x)^2}.$$

Clearly, this generating function can be very easily found by a trivial direct computation.

3. Intersection of two hooks

Now consider the intersection of two hooks of different shapes, say a $(h, k + l)$ -hook and a $(h + m, k)$ -hook. We denote by $\mathcal{P}_{h,l}^{m,k}$ the set of integer partitions fitting into such a shape.

Figure 3: The intersection of a $(4, 7)$ -hook and a $(7, 2)$ -hook.

We tackle the problem of determining the generating function $p_{h,l}^{m,k}(x)$ of the class $\mathcal{P}_{h,l}^{m,k}$. To this aim we need to recall some known definitions and results.

We start by defining the *q-shifted factorial of order k* to be the quantity

$$(x; q)_k = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (1 - xq^i).$$

The *q-binomial coefficients* are given by the expression

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(x; x)_a}{(x; x)_b (x; x)_{a-b}}.$$

The following result can be found in [1].

Lemma 3.1 *The generating function for the class of partitions which fit inside of a $k \times l$ rectangle is given by:*

$$\begin{bmatrix} k + l \\ l \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(x; x)_{k+l}}{(x; x)_k \cdot (x; x)_l}.$$

Now we are ready to state our main result.

Theorem 3.2 *The generating function for the partitions of $\mathcal{P}_{h,l}^{m,k}$ is given by:*

$$p_{h,l}^{m,k}(x) = p_{k,0}(x) \cdot \sum_{t=0}^h \left(\sum_{s=0}^{h+m-t} x^{s(k+1)} \cdot \left[\begin{matrix} l-1+s \\ s \end{matrix} \right] \right) p_{t,0}(x) x^{t(1+k+l)}. \tag{2}$$

Proof. We use a suitable modification of the argument employed in the previous theorem. Each partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k, \lambda_{k+1}, \dots, \lambda_{k+l}, \lambda_{k+l+1}, \dots, \lambda_r)$ fitting inside the intersection of two hooks of shapes $(h, k+l)$ and $(h+m, k)$ can be decomposed in a unique way into five partitions as follows:

- $\mu^{(1)} = (\lambda_{k+l+2}, \dots, \lambda_r)$ is constituted by the last $r - k - l - 1$ parts of λ ;
- $\mu^{(2)} = (\lambda_{k+l+1}^{k+l+1})$ is the rectangular-shaped partition having $k+l+1$ parts equal to λ_{k+l+1} ;
- $\mu^{(3)} = (\lambda_{k+2} - \lambda_{k+l+1}, \dots, \lambda_{k+l} - \lambda_{k+l+1})$ is a partition whose Ferrers diagram fits inside of a $(h+m - \lambda_{k+l+1}) \times (l-1)$ rectangle;
- $\mu^{(4)} = ((\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_{k+l+1})^{k+1})$ is the rectangular-shaped partition having $k+1$ parts equal to $\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_{k+l+1}$;
- $\mu^{(5)} = (\lambda_1 - \lambda_{k+1}, \dots, \lambda_k - \lambda_{k+1})$.

We point out that each of the $\mu^{(i)}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 5$) can be empty. Moreover, as we did in Theorem 2.1, in the previous expressions of the partitions $\mu^{(i)}$, we consider only those parts which are strictly positive. Figure 4 illustrates the above described decomposition.

Set $t = \lambda_{k+l+1}$ and $s = \lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_{k+l+1}$. Then it is easy to observe that t can range from 0 to h , whereas s runs from 0 to $h+m-t$. Putting all these things together, we find for the generating function $p_{h,l}^{m,k}(x)$ the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{h,l}^{m,k}(x) &= \sum_{t=0}^h p_{t,0}(x) \cdot x^{t(k+l+1)} \cdot \sum_{s=0}^{h+m-t} \left[\begin{matrix} l-1+s \\ s \end{matrix} \right] x^{s(k+1)} \cdot p_{k,0}(x) \\ &= p_{k,0}(x) \sum_{t=0}^h \left(\sum_{s=0}^{h+m-t} \left[\begin{matrix} l-1+s \\ s \end{matrix} \right] x^{s(k+1)} \right) p_{t,0}(x) x^{t(k+l+1)} \end{aligned}$$

as desired. □

This theorem has several special cases, some of which are recorded in the next corollaries.

Corollary 3.1 *If $m = l = 0$, we get the ordinary (h, k) -hook partitions, and the generating function (2) reduces to (1).*

Figure 4: The decomposition of a partition of $\mathcal{P}_{h,l}^{m,k}$.

Proof. Indeed, from general facts about q -binomial coefficients (see, for instance, [3]), we have that $\begin{bmatrix} a-1 \\ a \end{bmatrix} = 0$ for $a > 0$, and $\begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 1$, whence the corollary immediately follows. \square

Corollary 3.2 *The generating function of the class of partitions whose $(k + 1)$ -th part is at most $h + 1$ and the $(k + 2)$ -th is at most h is given by:*

$$\frac{p_{k,0}(x)}{1-x} \cdot \sum_{t=0}^h p_{t,0}(x)x^{t(k+2)}(1 - (x^{k-1})^{h+2-t}).$$

Proof. The class of partitions under consideration can be obtained by taking $l = m = 1$ in the above theorem. \square

Example. Call *quasi-hook partitions* those integer partitions whose parts are all equal to 1, except for the first one, which is arbitrary, and the second one, which must be at most 2. It is immediate to observe that quasi-hook partitions correspond to the case $l = m = h = k = 1$ in the previous corollary, so they have generating function

$$\frac{1 - x + x^2 + x^4}{(1 - x)^2}.$$

Also in this case, the same result can be found by direct computation.

References

- [1] G. E. Andrews, *The theory of partitions*, Encyclopedia of Mathematics and its Applications, 2, Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., Reading, Mass.-London-Amsterdam, 1976.
- [2] A. Berele, A.Regev, *Hook Young diagrams with applications to combinatorics and to representation theory of Lie superalgebras*, Adv. Math. 64 (1987) 118-175.
- [3] Ch. A. Charalambides, *Enumerative Combinatorics*, Chapman & Hall/CRC, Boca Raton, 2002.
- [4] L. Ferrari, R. Pinzani, S. Rinaldi, *Enumerative results on integer partitions using the ECO method*, in Mathematics and Computer Science, III (M. Drmota et al., eds.), Trends Math., Birkhäuser, Basel, 2004, pp. 25-36.
- [5] R. C. Orellana, M. Zabrocki, *Some remarks on the characters of the general Lie superalgebra*, arXiv:math.CO/0008152v1, 2000.
- [6] T. Seeman, private communication, 2003.